

**A STUDY OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF COOPERATIVE
LEARNING IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC
PERFORMANCE AT SECONDARY LEVEL**

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Abstract

In contrast to directed instruction where the teachers set the goals and deliver most of the instruction, the job of the teachers in constructivist model is to arrange for required resources and act as a guide to students while they set their own goals and 'teach themselves'. According to Johnson et al. (2002), cooperative learning is – 'teaching strategies and structures that involve students working together in small groups to maximize their own and other's learning'. In this study, it is an instructional approach where students are assigned in groups to expertise on a unique material after which they are reshuffled to form a new group wherein each member has to teach other what he/she specialized. 200 students and 120 teachers were the sample of this study. The sample was selected from the different schools of Allahabad district. Judgement tool, achievement test were used in the collection of data. The data were analyzed with the help of reliable and most suitable statistical techniques. The findings suggested significant effect of cooperative learning on students' academic performance also the teachers had favorable opinion about the use of cooperative learning strategies in the schools.

Key Words: *Cooperative Learning, Academic Performance, Secondary Level and Constructivism*

1. Introduction

With the changing facets of globalization and growth of competition between communities, the education of future generation is attracting critical attention. One of the functions of education as perceive by the public today is to prepare the youth of today to be the citizens and workers for the world of tomorrow. It is obvious that any attempt at the improvement in the quality of education is ultimately dependent on the quality of classroom instruction. It has been a common complaint among teachers, parents and

administrators that far too much valuable time in the classroom is consumed by creation of conducive learning environment and disciplinary measures. Most teachers expect students to listen, follow directions, turn in assignments and display self-control. Schools today are under great pressure to create safe, orderly learning environments that encourage social as well as academic skills that allow students to succeed in attainments of the required competencies in school and in their future endeavors. If we expect students to learn appropriate social and evaluative skills, we must structure the learning environment so that these skills can be addressed and practiced (Dollman et al., 2007). For this, appropriate pedagogic practices and episode of teaching and learning need to be evolved besides keeping track of child's interest and needs (Rao, 2004).

Unlike in the past, where cramming up and recalling was the main focus, a new approach to classroom learning has occurred wherein Gardner's Multiple Intelligence Theory is the main focus of education. As a result, the shift from teacher-centered learning to learner-centered education has occurred. The more recent pattern of education in our country emphasizes the technique of using competitive groups in classrooms. Such techniques provide greater opportunities for students to interact with varied learning environment stimulated by process-oriented teaching.

In a process-oriented conception of teaching, the learner should construct knowledge actively. Whereas, when teacher is transmitting facts and procedures, learning tends to be mainly absorption of knowledge. Such teacher dominant practice has been followed in the teaching.

A study by Panda (2004) shows that mathematics instruction involves disciplined inquiry into the nature and context of the processes teachers use to help learners develop their mathematical knowledge and abilities. Teachers are to help learners develop the required mathematical skills and abilities so that they become competent enough to face the global challenges. Greater attention

has to be given to both the process of instruction and to the context in which that instruction occurs.

2. Justification of the Study

Teaching is an art. It is argued that children must allow constructing their own meaning of the subject. The child's learning need is best fulfilled by allowing each child to pursue his/her unique interests in a relaxed atmosphere. The transaction of curriculum should no longer be process of imparting fixed body of knowledge, but of developing in students a capacity to learn by collecting information, formulating and testing hypotheses, making inferences and drawing rational conclusions. Classrooms that offer challenging should support students' achievements as well as their self-efficacy as learners and their performance for future challenges. Kagan (1988) argues that students to benefit from group work, requires a degree of tolerance and mutual understanding, the ability to articulate a point of view, to engage in discussion, reasoning, probing and questioning. Such skills are not in themselves innate, they have to be learnt and so taught.

Even though Uttar Pradesh is foremost in the adoption of certain efficacious activity-oriented approaches for the development of students' intrinsic motivation and innate capacities, we doubt whether there is any alignment in the set objectives and instructional outcome. The investigator, as a teacher educator for more than a decade, feels that the present system of education though activity oriented, is suitable only for a small percentage of students. This is true, as the performance of the group is mainly assessed on the basis of the performance of any member of that group; which implies that group activity followed in the current system fails to cater to individual needs. Moreover, research evidences of Willis (2007) and Faryadi (2007) show that during the periods of high stress of anxiety that some students may experience when asked to do math problem on the board or make an oral presentation to the class, their emotional state is associated with greatly heightened metabolism. Hence, there arose a need to go deeper into this pertinent issue and

find a solution to overcome the difficulties encountered in learning mathematics.

More recently, 'how primary children are best taught' has become a key consideration which was also a major concern for the leading educationists like Piaget, Bruner, Vygotsky and others. Their theories advocated that concepts can be attained concretely by a child at upper primary stage (10-12 years). It is for teachers to assess, how children's mind work while learning. Their views about how much learning takes place affect the ways in which they design learning opportunities for their pupils.

Hawk and Shah (2007) are of the opinion that faculty are likely to reach only some of the students in a given course, if they assume that all students learn the same way or that one teaching approach will suit all students. Thus, the faculty who are consciously aware of their students' learning styles as well as their own, are in a position to make more informed choices in course material and design learning processes to broaden the opportunities for effective learning in their courses.

Though the aforesaid studies done in foreign countries show that cooperative learning is a suitable method which caters to learn meaningful, very few studies have been done in India to find out the effectiveness of pedagogical teaching methods. Hence, the need for present study. The following research questions were formed on the basis of the study:

- Can the select pattern of cooperative learning be effectively adopted for learning in a relaxed and friendly atmosphere at secondary level?
- Do learn through cooperative learning approach have impact on their achievement?
- Can the performance of students be enhanced using cooperative learning approach?

3. Statement of the Problem

The present study intends to examine the effectiveness of the select method of cooperative learning namely the jigsaw pattern on the secondary students. The problem under the investigation is titled as-

“A Study of the Effectiveness of Cooperative Learning in relation to Academic Performance at Secondary level”.

4. Variables of the Study

The variables of the study are categorized as dependent and independent as given below:

4.1 Dependent Variable

The dependent variable considered in the study is the academic performance of an individual.

4.2. Independent Variables

The independent variables are-

- (a) Cooperative Learning Method
- (b) Current Activity Oriented Method

5. Objectives of the Study

The study mainly focused on attaining the following objectives:

- (i) To find out the relative effectiveness of cooperative learning over the current activity centered method on secondary students
- (ii) To analyze the opinion of secondary teachers and experts regarding the effectiveness of cooperative learning method

6. Hypothesis and Research Question

The following hypothesis and research question was formulated for the study:

- (i) There is no significant effect of cooperative learning over the current activity centered method on secondary students.
- (ii) Are secondary school teachers and experts having positive opinions regarding the effectiveness of cooperative learning method?

7. Sample

The sample selected for the study comprised of 200 9th standard students from 10 schools from Allahabad district of Uttar Pradesh and 120 teachers from secondary schools

8. Tools and Techniques

The followings tools and techniques were used:

- First term marks as the pre-score of the sample
- Achievement test (standardized by the investigator) as the post score of the sample
- The pre-scored and post-scores of the sample were subjected to the statistical techniques t-test and ANCOVA.
- Participant observation to assess the interaction pattern of students in cooperative learning groups.
- Self-evaluation Performa for students in the experimental group to analyze the effectiveness of cooperative learning method and
- Judgment Schedule to seek the opinion of teachers regarding the effectiveness of cooperative learning

9. Major Findings

The major findings were as follows:

After the analysis of the data obtained on comparison of various scores of the total sample confirms the aforesaid conclusions:

- The study found that the academic performance of students can be enhanced through cooperative learning.
- The result of the test of significance of the pre scores of the experimental and control groups of the total sample indicate that both groups were more or less similar in their initial performance. After administering the selected pattern of cooperative learning to the experimental group and the present activity oriented method to the control group, it was found that the two groups differ significantly (CR = 33.26; $p < 0.01$; mean control = 9.08; mean experimental = 20.01). From the obtained mean scores, it is clear that the mean of the experimental group is much higher than that of the

control group. While comparing the pre scores and post scores of the experimental group, it was observed that the post score of the experimental group was remarkably higher than the pre score. The effectiveness of cooperative learning was statistically established through ANCOVA wherein the F ratio obtained ($F_{yx} = 1308.5$) and t-value of the adjusted means ($t = 36.86$) are significant at 0.01 level of significance which implies the better performance of the experimental group. Thus, cooperative learning is found to be effective on students with their achievement. This is further supported by findings that emerged on analysis of the effectiveness on each parameter.

On the basis of results the investigator rejected the hypothesis and found there is significant effect of cooperative learning over the current activity centered method on secondary students.

Thus the teachers and experts have positive opinions regarding the effectiveness of cooperative learning method

10.Conclusions

The study throws light on the pedagogical teaching methods. The study found that cooperative learning; especially the jigsaw pattern is very effective for the conceptualization of different subjects in a collaborative atmosphere at secondary level. Students were found to benefit from each other by sharing their ideas and learning together. Individual accountability and interdependence among students was evidenced through this method. This method gave an opportunity to all students for self reflections.

11.Implications

- The findings of the study support the idea that with proper teacher facilitation and formation of cooperative groups, students are able to learn concepts effectively with higher levels of understand interaction, reflection and social skills.
- The results of this investigation may warrant the need to alert

educators and prospective teachers at secondary and primary level to integrate learning styles with complementary instructional methods in different subjects. Teacher should be trained to teach learners the procedure of learning together and how to manage group activities. In view of the benefits of cooperative learning for enhancing both academic achievement and social goals, schools must take a serious look at restructuring classrooms to provide for cooperation among students.

- Through this study the investigator initiates to develop cooperative learning environment, wherein the learners will enjoy learning and improve their critical thinking and intellectual skills by learning from one another. Students and not the teacher should be made responsible for accomplishing their tasks in the way they think best with accountability to each other and to the teacher's standard. Students should be encouraged to learn together and become a part and parcel of each other so as to benefit from each other's knowledge and skills.

- In addition to cooperative learning, teachers should be acquainted with other innovative strategies like reflective learning strategies and experiential learning strategies for making learning more meaningful.

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